

COST Action Final Achievement Report (03/11/2017 to 30/04/2022)

CA16204: Distant Reading for European Literary History

The Action was approved by the Committee of Senior Officials (CSO) on 23-6-2017 and has the MoU reference COST 015/17.

This report shows the data entered into e-COST to enable the Action Chair to verify the completeness and accuracy of the report with the MC prior to submitting the report via e-COST in fulfilment of the rules for COST Action Management, Monitoring and Final Assessment.

Action leadership and participants

Leadership positions

Position	Name	Contact details	Country*
Chair	Prof Christof Schöch	schoech@uni-trier.de +491773484840	Germany

Position	Name	Contact details	Country*
Vice Chair	Prof Maciej Eder	maciejeder@gmail.com +48 (12) 632-56-92	Poland

Working groups

#	WG Title	# of participants	WG Leader	Country*
1	Scholarly Resources	36	Dr Carolin Odebrecht carolin.odebrecht@hu-berlin.de	Germany
2	Methods and Tools	35	Ms Joanna Byszuk joanna.byszuk@ijp.pan.pl	Poland
3	Literary Theory and History	33	Prof Rosario Arias rarias@uma.es	Spain
4	Dissemination	12	Prof Katja Mihurko Poniž katja.mihurko.poniz@ung.si	Slovenia

Other key leadership positions

Position	Name	Contact details	Country*
Science Communication Coordinator	Prof Katja Mihurko Poniž	katja.mihurko.poniz@ung.si	Slovenia
GH Scientific Representative	Prof Christof Schöch	schoech@uni-trier.de	Germany

* The country displayed is:

- for the Action Chair, the country that nominated that person to the Management Committee before they were elected Action Chair;
- for the Vice Chair the country that nominated the person as a Management Committee Member,
- for all other leadership positions, if the person is a MC Member the country displayed is the country of nomination, otherwise it is the country of the person's primary work affiliation.

Participants

COST members having accepted the MoU

AL	02/11/2021	AT	08/05/2018	BE	26/09/2017	BA	23/08/2017	BG	12/09/2017
HR	25/09/2017	CY	02/11/2021	CZ	09/10/2017	DK	12/06/2018	EE	02/11/2021
FI	02/11/2021	FR	20/07/2017	GE	12/04/2022	DE	18/07/2017	EL	18/07/2017
HU	16/10/2017	IS	02/11/2021	IE	13/09/2017	IL	16/07/2017	IT	29/09/2017
LV	02/11/2017	LT	28/05/2018	LU	02/11/2021	MT	02/08/2017	MD	02/11/2021
ME	04/12/2017	NL	02/10/2017	MK	15/02/2018	NO	19/09/2017	PL	21/08/2017
PT	26/10/2017	RO	17/08/2017	RS	02/09/2017	SK	18/06/2020	SI	04/10/2017
ZA	02/11/2021	ES	22/08/2017	SE	17/06/2020	CH	07/09/2017	TR	02/11/2021
UA	12/04/2022	UK	07/08/2017						

Other participants

Institution Name	Country
------------------	---------

DRAFT

Summary

Main aim/ objective

This Action will develop the resources and methods necessary to change the way European literary history is written. Through a shared theoretical and practical framework, it will enable sophisticated computational methods of analysis of large collections of literary texts and foster insight into cross-national, large-scale evolutions across European literary traditions.

The Action addressed this as described below

In summary, the key objectives of this Action were the following: (1) To create a unique, multilingual, state-of-the-art, freely-accessible collection of comparable corpora of literary texts from across Europe. (2) To use this collection of corpora for an interdisciplinary and multilingual investigation of European literary history through suitable, innovative methods of text analysis. (3) To do so by mobilizing an emerging, European community of researchers who would spread and expand the knowledge of the required methods for the creation and analysis of such a collection of literary texts. We believe we have achieved all three of these high-level objectives: (1) The creation of the European Literary Text Collection (ELTeC) fulfils our first objective. (2) The large number of publications documenting the creation of ELTeC, the use of innovative methods for its annotation and analysis, as well as more theoretical papers on the consequences of digital texts and methods for literary history, fulfils our second objective. (3) And the large, diverse, committed and lively community of researchers from across Europe, and beyond, that has consolidated and expanded while working on these shared objectives, and that has been able to obtain significant amounts of new funding for projects associated with the Action, shows that we have also fulfilled our third goal. We are thankful that these key achievements of the Action, and the collective experience that we have gained as a community since 2017 through the Action, can now continue to grow and develop in a large-scale, cross-European project on "Computational Literary Studies Infrastructure" (CLS INFRA).

Action website

<https://www.distant-reading.net/>

Achievement of MoU objectives, deliverables and additional outputs/ achievements

MoU objectives

Please self-assess and describe the level of achievement of each MoU objective. For any MoU objectives that were less than 76% achieved please provide justification.

Please provide proof to enable the Action Rapporteur to confirm the level of achievement.

Mou objective	To coordinate the creation of a multilingual European Literary Text Collection (ELTeC) in three iterations.		
Type of objective	1.b Coordination of information seeking, identification, collection and/or data curation 2.b Building a community around a new or emerging field of research		
Level of achievement of MoU objective	76 - 100%	Dependence of achievement on the action networking	High
Proof of achievement of MoU objective	The European Literary Text Collection has been created. It currently contains 11 complete corpora, an additional 10 partially-complete collections, as well as 7 extension collections. A total of more than 2000 novels in 21 different languages are freely available and more will be added. See https://www.distant-reading.net/eltec/ for a list of resources on ELTeC and https://distantreading.github.io/ELTeC/ for the table of languages and novels included.		

Mou objective	To use the ELTeC to establish best practices and develop innovative methods of Distant Reading for the multiple European literary traditions.		
Type of objective	1.d Comparison and/or performance assessment of a theory, model, methodology, technology or technique 1.e Development of knowledge needing international coordination, pertaining to a new or improved theory, model, methodology, technology or technique		
Level of achievement of MoU objective	76 - 100%	Dependence of achievement on the action networking	High
Proof of achievement of MoU objective	Based on ELTeC (Objective 1), a wide range of innovative methods of Distant Reading methods for multiple European languages have been created. This has concerned a shared model for comparable linguistic annotation, an innovative procedure for making metadata available as linked open data on Wikidata, analyses of various aspects of the novels such as direct speech, the titling practices, stylometric aspects, thematic aspects, and many more things. This can best be checked using the list of Action publications available here: https://www.distant-reading.net/resources/publications/ .		

Mou objective	To engage in an investigation into the theoretical, methodological and practical consequences of Distant Reading approaches for literary history and literary theory.		
Type of objective	1.a Development of a common understanding/definition of the subject matter 1.d Comparison and/or performance assessment of a theory, model, methodology, technology or technique		
Level of achievement of MoU objective	76 - 100%	Dependence of achievement on the action networking	High
Proof of achievement of MoU objective	This objective has clearly been achieved, in particular through a series of publications on these matters. Proof of this can best be observed from the list of Action publications -- https://www.distant-reading.net/resources/publications/ -- and the list of Action presentations -- https://www.distant-reading.net/resources/presentations/ . That said, several papers relevant to this domain are either submitted or in still in progress at this		

	time.		
Mou objective	To foster the acquisition of state-of-the-art methods of Distant Reading, including competencies relating to data curation, standards, best practices and methods of Distant Reading analysis.		
Type of objective	2.b Building a community around a new or emerging field of research		
Level of achievement of MoU objective	76 - 100%	Dependence of achievement on the action networking	High
Proof of achievement of MoU objective	This objective has been fully achieved, notably through the 5 Training Schools organized by the Action, but also through the many STSMs and VMGs supported by the Action. The list of training schools can be obtained here: https://www.distant-reading.net/events/ , with additional information on each training school linked there.		
Mou objective	To encourage and support the submission of competitive grant proposals both at the national and European levels.		
Type of objective	2.c Bridging separate fields of science/disciplines to achieve breakthroughs that require an interdisciplinary approach		
Level of achievement of MoU objective	76 - 100%	Dependence of achievement on the action networking	High
Proof of achievement of MoU objective	This objective has been fully achieved. Evidence for this fact are the many funded projects that have emanated from the Action, at the national, bi-national and pan-European levels. The list of these projects is given in the relevant section of this report. The most important achievement in this area is certainly that a group of Action participants have obtained, together with partners related to DARIAH-EU, a Horizon 2020 Starting Community grant supporting the project "Computational Literary Studies Infrastructure" (CLS INFRA), funded from 2021 to 2025 with almost 5 million euros. See https://clsinfra.io for details.		
Mou objective	To help address the current gender imbalance among practitioners of Distant Reading research.		
Type of objective	2.e Building capacity in the demographic inclusiveness of networks in science and technology, including representation of newly established research groups, Early-Career Investigators, the under-represented gender and teams from countries/regions with less capacity in the field of the Action		
Level of achievement of MoU objective	76 - 100%	Dependence of achievement on the action networking	High
Proof of achievement of MoU objective	<p>On this topic, please also see the First Progress Report which focused on this issue. The data gathered for that report showed that the gender balance in our Action is quite well overall, although the numbers are slightly less balanced for the leadership roles. This is therefore an area on which we have focused on specifically in the year since the First Progress Report. However, it is an area where relatively few occasions for change occur in the short term. At two occasions to elect new persons to leadership roles, the Action has elected female candidates for these roles.</p> <p>When looking beyond MC membership and leadership roles, for example at gender balance at Action events and activities such as STSMs and Training Schools, we note that the selection criteria we have defined for STSM grantees and Training School grantees have a specific provision in favor of a gender balance in them and this clearly has effects.</p> <p>As far as Training Schools are concerned, at our Galway Training School, 19 (or 58%) of the participants have been female. As for the Budapest Training School, 22 (or 50%) of the participants have been female. Regarding STSMs, so far 9 out of 19 of STSM grantees (or 47%) have been female. While this is slightly less than half, the duration of the STSMs should also be considered. According to that metric, 172 out of a total of 320 STSM days (or 54%) can be attributed to female grantees.</p>		

DRAFT

Deliverables

This section covers only deliverables that were foreseen for the Action, not additional outputs that were generated during the Action (these additional outputs will be added in the following section). Please select and comment on the level of achievement of each deliverable as well as the extent to which the achievement was dependant on the Action networking.

For deliverables that are:

- Delivered, please provide proof to enable the Action Rapporteur to confirm the delivery
- Not delivered but delivery is foreseen within 2 years please explain how the delivery will be achieved
- Not foreseen to be delivered please explain why not

Deliverable	Milestone M-0-1: "Progress Report 1" with information on the progress achieved since the start of the Action (responsibility: Management Committee).		
Level of achievement of deliverable	Delivered	Dependence of achievement on the action networking	High
Proof of achievement of deliverable	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6591101		

Deliverable	Milestone M-0-2: "Progress Report 2" with information on the progress of the Action since the the first progress report (responsibility: Management Committee).		
Level of achievement of deliverable	Delivered	Dependence of achievement on the action networking	High
Proof of achievement of deliverable	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6591103		

Deliverable	Milestone M-0-3: "Final Achievement Report" with an overview over the Action's achievements during the entire lifespan (responsibility: Management Committee).		
Level of achievement of deliverable	Delivered	Dependence of achievement on the action networking	High
Proof of achievement of deliverable	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6591107		

Deliverable	Milestone M-1-1: The ELTeC, first iteration: subcollections for 6 languages (responsibility: Working Group 1).		
Level of achievement of deliverable	Delivered	Dependence of achievement on the action networking	High
Proof of achievement of deliverable	https://distantreading.github.io/ELTeC/		

Deliverable	Milestone M-1-2: The ELTeC, second iteration: subcollections in at least 4 additional languages (responsibility: Working Group 1).		
Level of achievement of deliverable	Delivered	Dependence of achievement on the action networking	High
Proof of achievement of deliverable	https://distantreading.github.io/ELTeC/		

Deliverable	Milestone M-1-3: The ELTeC, third iteration: at least 6 expansion subcollections (responsibility: Working Group 1).		
Level of achievement of deliverable	Delivered	Dependence of achievement on the action networking	High
Proof of achievement of deliverable	https://distantreading.github.io/ELTeC/		

Deliverable	Milestone M-2-1: Journal paper on benchmarking and language-dependent performance evaluation of existing methods using ELTeC (responsibility: Working Group 2).		
Level of achievement of deliverable	Delivered	Dependence of achievement on the action networking	High
Proof of achievement of deliverable	https://doi.org/10.3390/math10050838		

Deliverable	Milestone M-2-2: Journal paper summarizing the results of evaluating existing Distant Reading tools and strategies for improvement (responsibility: Working Group 2).		
Level of achievement of deliverable	Delivered	Dependence of achievement on the action networking	High
Proof of achievement of deliverable	https://lrec2020.lrec-conf.org/media/proceedings/Workshops/Books/LT4HALAbook.pdf		

Deliverable	Milestone M-2-3: "Lessons-learned"-report about cross-linguistic use of Distant Reading Methods (responsibility: Working Group 2).		
Level of achievement of deliverable	Not foreseen	Dependence of achievement on the action networking	High
Explanation	Instead of one report on all lessons learned, multiple more specific publications have been produced where this aspect of the project is relevant.		

Deliverable	Milestone M-3-1: Journal paper outlining concepts like genre, style and authorship in computational and non-computational literary history (responsibility: Working Group 3).		
Level of achievement of deliverable	Not delivered, but foreseen within 2 years	Dependence of achievement on the action networking	High
Explanation	This paper has proved to be particularly challenging, but has been submitted in early 2022 and is currently under review.		

Deliverable	Milestone M-3-2: Journal paper outlining different approaches to literary periodization and canonization in relation to literary history and Distant Reading (responsibility: Working Group 3).		
Level of achievement of deliverable	Not foreseen	Dependence of achievement on the action networking	High
Explanation	This topic is included in the paper mentioned in deliverable 10, so a separate publication is no longer foreseen.		

--	--	--	--

Deliverable	Milestone M-3-3: Journal paper on theoretical assumptions and foundations of Distant Reading research (responsibility: Working Group 3).		
Level of achievement of deliverable	Not foreseen	Dependence of achievement on the action networking	Medium
Explanation	The interest of the group have turned to other topics and this paper has not been written.		

Deliverable	Milestone M-4-1: Guidelines for a dissemination strategy, supporting the other WGs and the MC (responsibility: Working Group 4).		
Level of achievement of deliverable	Delivered	Dependence of achievement on the action networking	High
Proof of achievement of deliverable	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3465809		

Deliverable	Milestone 4-4-2: The Action's portal is functional and online, ready to host the ELTeC (responsibility: Working Group 4).		
Level of achievement of deliverable	Delivered	Dependence of achievement on the action networking	High
Proof of achievement of deliverable	https://distant-reading.net		

Deliverable	Milestone M-4-3: The Final Action Dissemination materials are available (responsibility: Working Group 4).		
Level of achievement of deliverable	Delivered	Dependence of achievement on the action networking	High
Proof of achievement of deliverable	https://www.distant-reading.net/		

Additional outputs / achievements

Co-authored Action publications

Please enter below ONLY publications (including publications that are submitted but not yet accepted):

- that are on the topic of the Action, and
- that are co-authored by at least two Action participants from two countries participating in the Action, and
- for which the Action networking was necessary.

Please pay special attention to the COST Excellence and Inclusiveness policy and ensure the inclusion of publications with authors from COST Inclusiveness Target Countries (ITCs), from the underrepresented gender in the Action and from Early Career Investigators/Young researchers.

	Bibliographic data	Countries participating in the Action among authors	Open Access	COST cited?	COST funds?	Relevance to H2020 Societal challenge	Peer Reviewed?
1	<p>doi:10.5281/zenodo.1297690</p> <p>Christof Schöch, Maciej Eder, Carolin Odebrecht, Mike Kestemont, Antonija Primorac, Justin Tonra: "Distant Reading for European Literary History. A COST Action". In: Digital Humanities Conference 2018: Book of Abstracts. Mexico City: ADHO, 2018. URL: https://dh2018.adho.org/distant-reading-for-european-literary-history-a-cost-action/ (peer-reviewed abstract; poster)</p>	BE, HR, DE, IE, PL	Y	Y	N	Europe in a changing world, inclusive innovative and reflective societies	Y
2	<p>doi:10.5281/zenodo.3546325</p> <p>Carolin Odebrecht, Lou Burnard, Borja Navarro Colorado, Maciej Eder, Christof Schöch: "The European Literary Text Collection ELTeC". Digital Humanities Conference 2019: Book of Abstracts. Utrecht: ADHO, 2019.</p>	DE, PL, ES, UK	Y	Y	N	Europe in a changing world, inclusive innovative and reflective societies	Y
3		DE, ES, UK	Y	Y	N	Europe in a changing world, inclusive	N

	<p>Carolyn Odebrecht, Lou Burnard, Borja Navarro-Colorado (with all WG1 members): <i>ELTeC Guidelines. Web-accessible versions of discussion documents</i>. URL: https://distantreading.github.io/ (Contains "Sampling Criteria for the ELTeC", "Encoding Guidelines for the ELTeC", "Workflow proposal" as well as further documents that, taken together, form the conceptual and practical basis for the creation of ELTeC (objective #1 and deliverable #4).</p>					innovative and reflective societies	
4	<p>doi:10.5281/zenodo.3552488</p> <p>Lou Burnard, Christof Schöch and Carolyn Odebrecht: "In Search of Comity: TEI for Distant Reading". What is text, really? TEI and beyond. Book of Abstracts. Graz: ZIM, 2019. https://graz-2019.tei-c.org/program/book-of-abstracts/</p>	DE, UK	Y	Y	N	Europe in a changing world, inclusive innovative and reflective societies	Y
5	<p>doi:10.3390/math10050838</p> <p>Title Parallel Stylometric Document Embeddings with Deep Learning Based Language Models in Literary Authorship Attribution</p> <p>Authors Mihailo Škorić; Ranka Stanković; Milica Ikonić Nešić; Joanna Byszuk; Maciej Eder</p> <p>DOI doi:10.3390/math10050838</p> <p>Type Journal article</p> <p>Published in Mathematics</p> <p>Published by MDPI AG</p> <p>ISSN 2227-7390</p> <p>Subjects General Mathematics; Engineering (miscellaneous); Computer Science (miscellaneous)</p> <p>Link https://www.mdpi.com/2227-7390/10/5/838/pdf</p>		Other	Y	Y		Y
6	<p>doi:10.18485/infoteca.2021.21.2.1</p> <p>Title The Serbian Part of the ELTeC – from the Empty List to the 100 Novels Collection</p> <p>Authors Aleksandra Trtovac; Vasilije Milnović;</p>		Other	Y	Y		Y

	<p>DOI Type Published in Published by</p> <p>ISSNs Subject</p>	<p>Cvetana Krstev doi:10.18485/infoteca.2021.21.2.1 Journal article Infotheca Faculty of Philology, University of Belgrade doi:10.18485/infoteca.2021.21.2.1 General Engineering</p>						
7	<p>doi:10.18485/infoteca.2021.21.2.2 Title</p> <p>Author DOI Type Published in Published by</p> <p>ISSNs Subject</p>	<p>The Serbian Part of the ELTeC Collection Through the Magnifying Glass of Metadata Cvetana Krstev doi:10.18485/infoteca.2021.21.2.2 Journal article Infotheca Faculty of Philology, University of Belgrade doi:10.18485/infoteca.2021.21.2.2 General Engineering</p>		Other	Y	Y		Y
8	<p>doi:10.18485/infoteca.2021.21.2.3 Title</p> <p>Authors</p> <p>DOI Type Published in Published by</p> <p>ISSNs Subject</p>	<p>Annotation of the Serbian ELTeC Collection Ranka Stanković; Cvetana Krstev; Branislava Šandrih Todorović; Mihailo Škorić doi:10.18485/infoteca.2021.21.2.3 Journal article Infotheca Faculty of Philology, University of Belgrade doi:10.18485/infoteca.2021.21.2.3 General Engineering</p>		Other	Y	Y		Y
9	<p>doi:10.18485/infoteca.2021.21.2.4 Title</p> <p>Authors</p>	<p>Serbian ELTeC Sub-Collection in Wikidata Milica Ikonić Nešić; Ranka Stanković; Biljana Rujević</p>		Other	Y	Y		Y

	<p>DOI Type Published in Published by</p> <p>ISSNs Subject</p>	<p>doi:10.18485/infotheca.2021.21.2.4 Journal article Infotheca Faculty of Philology, University of Belgrade 1450-9687; 2217-9461 General Engineering</p>						
10	<p>doi:10.18485/infotheca.2021.21.2.7 Title Authors DOI Type Published in Published by</p> <p>ISSNs Subject</p>	<p>SrpELTeC on Platforms: <i>Udaljeno čitanje</i>, Aurora, NoSketch Ranka Stanković; Mihailo Škorić; Petar Popović doi:10.18485/infotheca.2021.21.2.7 Journal article Infotheca Faculty of Philology, University of Belgrade 1450-9687; 2217-9461 General Engineering</p>		Other	Y	Y		Y
11	<p>doi:10.3828/mlo.v0i0.364 Title Authors DOI Type Published in Published by ISSN Subjects</p>	<p>Creating the European Literary Text Collection (ELTeC): Challenges and Perspectives Christof Schöch; Roxana Patras; Tomaž Erjavec; Diana Santos doi:10.3828/mlo.v0i0.364 Journal article Modern Languages Open Liverpool University Press 2052-5397 General Engineering; Energy Engineering and Power Technology</p>		Other	Y	Y		Y
12	<p>doi:10.4000/jtei.3500 Title Authors DOI</p>	<p>In search of comity: TEI for distant reading Lou Burnard; Christof Schöch; Carolin Odebrecht doi:10.4000/jtei.3500</p>		Other	Y	Y		Y

	Type Published in Published by ISSN Subjects	Journal article Journal of the Text Encoding Initiative OpenEdition 2162-5603 Industrial and Manufacturing Engineering; Polymers and Plastics; Business and International Management					
13	Cinková, Silvie, and Jan Rybicki, 'Stylometry in a Bilingual Setup', in Proceedings of The 12th Language Resources and Evaluation Conference, LREC 2020, Marseille, France, May 11-16, 2020, ed. by Nicoletta Calzolari, Frédéric Béchet, Philippe Blache, Khalid Choukri, Christopher Cieri, Thierry Declerck, and others (presented at the 12th Language Resources and Evaluation Conference, LREC 2020, Marseille: European Language Resources Association, 2020), pp. 977–984, https://www.aclweb.org/anthology/2020.lrec-1.123/	CZ, PL	Y	Y	N	Europe in a changing world, inclusive innovative and reflective societies	Y
14	Byszuk, Joanna, Michał Woźniak, Mike Kestemont, Albert Leśniak, Wojciech Łukasik, Artjoms Šeļa, and others, 'Detecting Direct Speech in Multilingual Collection of 19th Century Novels', in Proceedings of LT4HALA 2020-1st Workshop on Language Technologies for Historical and Ancient Languages, ed. by Rachele Sprungoli and Marco Passarotti (presented at the LT4HALA 2020: 1st Workshop on Language Technologies for Historical and Ancient Languages, Paris: European Language Resources Association (ELRA), 2020), pp. 100–104, https://lrec2020.lrec-conf.org/media/proceedings/Workshops/Books/LT4HALAbook.pdf .	BE, PL	Y	Y	N	Europe in a changing world, inclusive innovative and reflective societies	Y
15	Patras, Roxana, Ioana Galleron, Camelia GRĂDINARU, Ioana Lionte, and Lucreția Pascaru, 'The Splendors and Mist(Eries) of Romanian Digital Literary Studies: A State-of-the-Art Just before Horizons 2020 Closes Off', <i>Hermeneia</i> , 23 (2019), 207–22 < http://hermeneia.ro/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/18_Patras-et-al.pdf > [accessed 17 February 2020]	FR, RO	Y	Y	N	Europe in a changing world, inclusive innovative and reflective societies	Y

Projects resulting from Action activities

Please enter below all the projects on the topic of the Action resulting from Action activities, involving at least one Action participant, and for which the Action networking was necessary.

The Action reported 7 project(s) and 3 proposal(s) resulting from the Action networking.

Key details of the projects are shown below.

#	Title	Countries participating in the Action among proposers	Main proposer name	Funder	Amount	Call identifier	Relevance to H2020 Soc challenge
1	Modeling of Complexity in Literary Texts	CZ	Silvie Cinkova	National	186500 €	Interexcellence-Intercost, ID LTC180320	Europe in a changing world, inclusive innovative and reflective societies
2	Zeta and Company. Measures of Distinctiveness for Computational Literary Studies	DE	Christof Schöch	National	467950 €	DFG, SPP 2270, ID 424211690	Europe in a changing world, inclusive innovative and reflective societies
3	Hajduk Novels in Romania During the Long Nineteenth Century: Digital Edition and Corpus Analysis Assisted by Computational Tools	FR, RO	Roxana Patras	National	15000 €	PN-III-P3-3.1-P M-RO-FR-2019	Europe in a changing world, inclusive innovative and reflective societies
4	Romane românești pentru Distant Reading – ELTeC: digitizare, procesare conform standardelor TEI-xml și validare	RO	Roxana Patras	National	5000 €	PNCDI III 2015-2020, P1: Dezvoltarea sistemului național cercetare dezvoltare, Subprogramul	Europe in a changing world, inclusive innovative and reflective societies

						1.1. Resurse umane, Proiecte de Mobilitate pentru cercetători 2019	
5	Gender and Spiritism in Nineteenth-century Andalusia (1840-1920): Gendered Networks and Borderlands / Género y espiritismo en Andalucía (1840-1920): enfoque filológico y traductológico	HR, ES	Rosario Arias	National	23979 €	UMA18-FEDER JA-167	Europe in a changing world, inclusive innovative and reflective societies
6	Deep Learning in Computational Stylistics	BE, PL	Mike Kestemont	Trans-national	25000 €	FWO/PAS	Europe in a changing world, inclusive innovative and reflective societies
7	Computational Literary Studies Infrastructure	DE, IE, NL	Maciej Eder	H2020 - Horizon Europe	4999941 €	H2020-INFRAIA-2018-2020	Europe in a changing world, inclusive innovative and reflective societies

Other outputs / achievements

Please enter below any additional outputs/ achievements on the topic of the Action that contribute to the COST mission: “COST enables break-through scientific developments leading to new concepts and products and thereby contributes to strengthen Europe’s research and innovation capacities”, and for which the Action networking was necessary (e.g. a patent, standards, white paper).

Output / achievement description	Dependence of achievement on the Action networking
Series of videos with statements by several Action participants explaining their perspective on "Distant Reading".	High
Journal article (single author): Luiza Marinescu (2019): "From Close to Distant Reading of 100 Romanian Novels". In: Studia ubb Philologia LXIV.2, 239-250, DOI: https://doi.org/10.24193/subbphilo.2019.2.19	Medium
Journal article (single author): Borja Navarro-Colorado (2018): "On Poetic Topic Modeling: Extracting Themes and Motifs From a Corpus of Spanish Poetry", in: Frontiers in Digital Humanities 5:15, DOI: https://doi.org/10.3389/fdigh.2018.00015	Low

Conference paper: Silvie Cinková, Tomaž Erjavec, Cláudia Freitas, Ioana Galleron, Péter Horváth, Christian-Emil Ore, Pavel Smrž and Balázs Indig: "Evaluation of taggers for 19th-century fiction", Budapest_DH 2019. URL: http://elte-dh.hu/dhprogram2019/ (Programme) URL: http://elte-dh.hu/wp-content/uploads/2019/09/DH_BP_2019-Abstract-Booklet.pdf (Book of Abstracts)	High
Conference paper: Isabel Araújo Branco, Diana Santos, Paulo Silva Pereira and Raquel Amaro: "A ação COST e o que representa e representou para a leitura distante em português / The COST action and what it represents and represented for distant reading in Portuguese". First Workshop on Distant Reading in Portuguese. Oslo: University of Oslo, 27-28 October 2019.	High
Conference paper: Primorac, Antonija. 2019. "Infrastructural Challenges for Large Scale Digital Text Corpora: A View From the European Margins." presented at the Humanities, Arts and Culture Data Summit and DARIAH Beyond Europe workshop, National Library of Australia, Canberra, March 28. https://www.humanities.org.au/special-event-1903/ .	Medium
Talk: Christof Schöch, „Distant Reading for European Literary History: A COST Action“, <i>DARIAH Text and Data Analysis Working Group Meeting, DARIAH Annual Event 2018</i> , Paris, 22.-24.5.2018. http://dariah-tda.github.io/meeting/activity/workshop/2018/05/11/WG-Meeting-Paris-2018.html	Medium
Talk: Christof Schöch, „The COST Action Distant Reading for European Literary History“, UA-DAAD Exchange Meeting, org. Hugh Craig, Newcastle University, March 21, 2018.	High
Keynote: Christof Schöch, „Repeating and Repeatable: Distant Reading between Past and Future“, <i>DH_Budapest 2019</i> , Budapest, September 25-27, 2019. http://elte-dh.hu/conf2019/	High
Journal article: Arias, Rosario y Juan-José Martín-González. "Distant Reading vs. Close Reading: Las nuevas tecnologías y la crítica literaria". <i>Las Humanidades en el mundo digital / El mundo digital en las Humanidades</i> . Valencia: Tirant, 2019. 342-49.	High
Conference paper: Cvetana Krstev, Jelena Jačimović, Branislava Šandrih and Ranka Stanković: "Analysis of the first Serbian literature corpus of the late 19th and early 20th century with the TXM platform". DH_Budapest 2019. Budapest: ELTE, 2019. http://elte-dh.hu/dhprogram2019/	High
Conference paper: Ranka Stankovic, Diana Santos, Francesca Frontini, Tomaž Erjavec and Carmen Brando: "Named entity recognition for distant reading in several european literatures. DH_Budapest 2019. Budapest: ELTE, 2019. http://elte-dh.hu/dhprogram2019/	High
Conference paper: Silvie Cinková, Tomaž Erjavec, Cláudia Freitas, Ioana Galleron, Péter Horváth, Christian-Emil Ore, Pavel Smrž and Balázs Indig: "Evaluation of taggers for 19th-century fiction." DH_Budapest 2019. Budapest: ELTE, 2019. http://elte-dh.hu/dhprogram2019/	High
Conference paper: Silvie Cinková and Jan Rybicki: "Stylometry in literary translation via universal dependencies: finally breaking the language barrier?" DH_Budapest 2019. Budapest: ELTE, 2019. http://elte-dh.hu/dhprogram2019/	Medium
Conference paper submission: Herrmann, J. Berenike; Odebrecht, Carolin; Santos, Diana; Francois, Pieter: "Towards Modeling the European Novel. Introducing ELTeC for Multilingual and Pluricultural Distant Reading", Digital Humanities Conference 2020.	High
Conference paper submission: Ore, Christian-Emil; Herrmann, Berenike; Odebrecht, Carolin; Santos, Diana: "ELTeC: A comparable corpus of novels in many European literatures", Digital Humanities in the Nordic Countries 2020 (DHN2020).	High

Distant Reading Recommends series of blog posts. See: https://www.distant-reading.net/category/distant-reading-recommends/	High
Škorić, Mihailo, 'Short Term Scientific Mission to Krakow: Comparative Stylistic and Morphosyntactic Analysis of ELTeC Texts Using Stylo R Package', <i>Infotheca - Journal for Digital Humanities</i> , 21.2 (2021) < https://infoteka.bg.ac.rs/ojs/index.php/Infoteka/article/view/2021.21.2.11_en >	Medium
Škorić, Mihailo, 'Workshop "Methods and Tools of Distant Reading Adapted to Multiple European Languages" at the Galway Training School', <i>Infotheca - Journal for Digital Humanities</i> , 21.2 (2021), 158–60 < https://infoteka.bg.ac.rs/ojs/index.php/Infoteka/article/view/2021.21.2.9_en >	Medium
Vitas, Duško, 'From Onions to Champagne – Food and Drink in the SrpELTeC Corpus', <i>Infotheca</i> , 21.2 (2021), 88–118 < https://doi.org/10.18485/infotheca.2021.21.2.5 >	Medium
Stanković, Ranka, 'Distant Reading Training School 2020: Named Entity Recognition & Geo-Tagging for Literary Analysis', <i>Infotheca - Journal for Digital Humanities</i> , 21.2 (2021), 167–71 < https://infoteka.bg.ac.rs/ojs/index.php/Infoteka/article/view/223 >	Medium
Krstev, Cvetana, and Ranka Stanković, 'Novels and Authors of the Serbian ELTeC Collection', <i>Infotheca - Journal for Digital Humanities</i> , 21.2 (2021) < https://infoteka.bg.ac.rs/ojs/index.php/Infoteka/article/view/2021.21.2.13_en >	Medium
Krstev, Cvetana, 'White as Snow, Black as Night – Similes in Old Serbian Literary Texts', <i>Infotheca</i> , 21.2 (2021), 119–36 < https://doi.org/10.18485/infotheca.2021.21.2.6 >	Medium
Krstev, Cvetana, 'Ideas and Observations from the Time of the ELTeC Corpus - a Selection of Quotations', <i>Infotheca - Journal for Digital Humanities</i> , 21.2 (2021) < https://infoteka.bg.ac.rs/ojs/index.php/Infoteka/article/view/2021.21.2.14_en >	Medium
Andonovski, Jelena, 'OCR and TEI for the Production of ELTeC - Würzburg Training School, 16-17 April 2018', <i>Infotheca - Journal for Digital Humanities</i> , 21.2 (2021) < https://infoteka.bg.ac.rs/ojs/index.php/Infoteka/article/view/2021.21.2.8_en >	Medium
Tonra, Justin, 'These Quick-Reading Times: Distant Reading Moore's Poetic Style', in <i>Write My Name: Authorship in the Poetry of Thomas Moore, Poetry and Song in the Age of Revolution</i> , 9 (New York; Abingdon: Routledge, 2020), pp. 127–66 < http://doi.org/10.4324/9781003090960-6 >	Medium
Santos, Diana, Emanuel Pires, Cláudia Freitas, Rebeca Schumacher Fuão, and João Marques Lopes, 'Periodização automática: Estudos linguístico-estatísticos de literatura lusófona', <i>Linguamática</i> , 12.1 (2020), 80–95 < https://linguamatica.com/index.php/linguamatica/article/view/314/465 >	Medium
Santos, Diana, Emanuel Pires, Cláudia Freitas, Rebeca Schumacher Fuão, and João Marques Lopes, 'Periodização automática: Estudos linguístico-estatísticos de literatura lusófona', <i>Linguamática</i> , 12.1 (2020), 80–95 < https://linguamatica.com/index.php/linguamatica/article/view/314/465 >	Medium
Krstev, Cvetana, Jelena Jaćimović, and Duško Vitas, 'Analysis of Similes in Serbian Literary Texts (1860-1920) Using Computational Methods', in <i>Proceedings of the Fourth International Conference Computational Linguistics in Bulgaria (CLIB 2020)</i> (presented at the Computational Linguistics in Bulgaria (CLIB 2020), Sofia: Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, 2020), pp. 31–41 < https://dcl.bas.bg/clib/wp-content/uploads/2020/06/CLIB2020_PROCEEDINGS_v1.0.pdf >	Medium
Marinescu, Luiza, 'From Close to Distant Reading of 100 Romanian Novels', <i>Studia Ubb Philologia</i> , LXIV.2 (2019), 239–50 < https://doi.org/10.24193/subbphilo.2019.2.19 >	Medium

Keturakis, Saulius, 'Apie skaitymą iš toli ir iš arti [About Distant and Close Reading]', LOGOS, 99 (2019), 103–12 < https://doi.org/10.24101/logos.2019.34 >	Medium
Jaćimović, Jelena, 'Textometric Methods and the TXM Platform for Corpus Analysis and Visual Presentation', Infotheca - Journal for Digital Humanities, 19.1 (2019), 30–54 < https://doi.org/10.18485/infotheca.2019.19.1.2 >	Medium
Tonra, Justin, 'What Is Distant Reading?', RTÉ Brainstorm, 2019 < https://www.rte.ie/brainstorm/2019/1114/1090846-what-is-distant-reading/ > [accessed 19 November 2019]	Medium
Santos, Diana, 'Doctors in Lusophone Literature', Digital Literary Stylistics, 2019 < https://dls.hypotheses.org/952 >	Medium
Koch, Marion, 'Data-Science trifft Schönggeist', Merton. Onlinemagazin des Stifterverbands, 7 December 2018 < https://merton-magazin.de/data-science-trifft-schoengeist >	Medium
Schöch, Christof, Europäische Literaturgeschichte. Ein Gespräch mit Christof Schöch, 2018 < https://www.uni-trier.de/fileadmin/fb2/LDV/DH/digital-humanities.wav >	Medium
SP, 'Die europäische Literaturgeschichte wird neu geschrieben. Digital Humanities an Uni Trier bereiten Literatur neu auf', Wochenspiegel (Trier, 4 September 2018) < https://www.wochenspiegelive.de/trier/stadt-trier/artikel/die-europaeische-literaturgeschichte-wird-neu-geschrieben-53978/ >	Medium
Mihurko-Poniž, Katja, Rosario Arias, J. Berenike Herrmann, Cvetana Krstev, Carolin Odebrecht, Christof Schöch, and others, 'Thresholds to the "Great Unread": Titling Practices across Multilingual Collections of European Novels' (presented at the Day of DH 2021, Rempte Event, 2021) < https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=fMtkwCzkzfw >	High
Frontini, Francesca, Carmen Brando, Joanna Byszuk, Ioana Galleron, Diana Santos, and Ranka Stanković, 'Named Entity Recognition for Distant Reading in ELTeC', 2020 < https://www.clarin.eu/event/2020/clarin-annual-conference-2020-virtual-form >	High
Schöch, Christof, Maciej Eder, Rosario Arias, Pieter François, and Antonija Primorac, 'Foundations of Distant Reading. Historical Roots, Conceptual Development and Theoretical Assumptions around Computational Approaches to Literary Texts' (unpublished Virtual Conference Presentation presented at the DH2020 Virtual Conference, Ottawa, 2020) < https://dh2020.hcommons.org/ >	High
Schöch, Christof, Karina van Dalen-Oskam, Maria Antoniak, Fotis Jannidis, and David Mimno, 'Replication and Computational Literary Studies' (unpublished Virtual Conference Panel presented at the DH2020 Virtual Conference, Ottawa, 2020) < https://hcommons.org/deposits/item/hc:30439/ >	High
Herrmann, J. Berenike, Carolin Odebrecht, Diana Santos, and Pieter François, 'Towards Modeling the European Novel. Introducing ELTeC for Multilingual and Pluricultural Distant Reading' (unpublished Virtual Conference Presentation presented at the DH2020 Virtual Conference, Ottawa, 2020) < https://dh2020.hcommons.org/ >	High

Impacts

Please describe the impacts (the short- to long-term scientific, technological, and / or socioeconomic changes produced by a COST Action, directly or indirectly, intended or unintended) that have resulted, or might result, from the Action in the following table (one impact per line).

Description of the impact, i.e. what will change, and for whom, as a result of what the Action achieved	Type of impact	Timing of impact
Computational analyses of the ELTeC collections will have an impact on the way European literary history is studied and understood. This impact will start to be felt towards the end of the Action and hopefully continue well-beyond the end of the Action.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scientific / Technological 	—
The availability of ELTeC will enable (a) comparative research into the history of the European novel and (b) cross-language evaluation studies of computational methods for literary text analysis.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scientific / Technological 	—
The collaboration of corpus linguistics, computational linguists, computational literary scholars and literary historians will strongly contribute to increase the exchanges and collaboration between these distinct, but in fact connected, fields. This is already the case inside the Action but will expand beyond the Action over the coming years.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scientific / Technological 	—
The best practices we have established in the Action with regard to corpus building (corpus composition criteria, encoding principles, integrated annotation, collaborative curation and open access publication) are highly likely to have the impact we hope for, that is, to serve as a showcase and a best practice example well beyond the Action.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scientific / Technological 	—
Action members have gained considerable experience with the challenges involved in collaboratively building a large-scale, multilingual textual resource and have documented our strategy to deal with these challenges in a detailed manner through the white papers on selection criteria and corpus composition as well as on Text Encoding Principles.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scientific / Technological 	Achieved
All Action contacts, of which there are close to 200 across all categories (regular MC members, substitute MC members, trainers, trainees, STSM grantees) have become part of our international network.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scientific / Technological 	Achieved
Through the different grant proposals submitted by Action members in the context of the Action, the proposers have in some cases gained freedom from other tasks to do more research related to the Action and to their research interests, and in some cases been able to hire researchers and form teams that allow them to achieve more progress with their research. (This impact has been achieved in several cases and we hope to add several more cases until and beyond the end of the Action.)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scientific / Technological 	Achieved
Action members have obtained, so far and in total, around 5,723,428 EUR in third-party funding through Action-related grant proposals. (This impact has already been achieved and we expect to see more proposals to be submitted by the Action members after the Action has ended.)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scientific / Technological 	Achieved

Please describe how the Action has advanced careers, skills and network of researchers, including Early Career Investigators (for example: joint supervision of graduate and PhD students, research exchanges not funded by the action, collaborations, Training Schools with ECTS accreditation, joint projects, internship and job prospects).

The Action has been advancing the careers, skills and network of researchers, including ECIs through Training Schools, STSMs and VMGs, support for submitting additional grant proposals, positions in funded grant proposals, new and improved skills in a range of digital research methods, and through other activities.

The career benefits were mainly to researchers with the following amount of experience after their PhD: ≤ 8 years.

Which of the stakeholders described in the “Plan for involving the most relevant stakeholders” in the Action’s MoU have been engaged and how? What additional stakeholders have been, or will be, engaged and how? This information will not be included in the Action Report that is made publicly available (on the website).

We have engaged with established researchers, early-career investigators, members of the library world, as well as the wider public interested in European cultural heritage.

DRAFT

Dissemination and exploitation of Action results (other than co-authored Action publications listed previously)

Please describe the Action's dissemination and exploitation approach as well as all activities undertaken to ensure dissemination and exploitation of the Action results and the effectiveness of these activities.

Dissemination and exploitation approach of the Action

The key output of the Action is the European Literary Text Collection (ELTeC). It is publicly and freely available on Github and via releases on Zenodo. In addition, we are making it available through additional challenges and in additional formats. We ensure uptake by readers for example by providing a simple HTML format and the "Distant Reading Recommends" blog series -- <https://www.distant-reading.net/category/distant-reading-recommends/> --. We are supporting uptake of ELTeC in research through the various aspects of documentation around its content and structure, notably through the ELTeC summary page --- <https://distantreading.github.io/ELTeC/> -- and several papers describing the creation of ELTeC, among them Schöch et al. 2021 -- <https://doi.org/10.3828/mlo.v0i0.364> -- and Burnard et al 2021 -- <https://doi.org/10.4000/jtei.3500> --.

Dissemination

Dissemination meetings funded by the Action

Title of Dissemination meeting	Meeting date	Meeting country	Action participant	Event name and hyperlink to the website	Title of presentation	Description of added value to the Action
N/A						

Other dissemination activities

E.g. participation to non-Action meetings, e.g. EU Parliament, meetings with policy makers, experts in the field, regional authorities.

Item/activity	Target audience	Outcome	Hyperlink
WG4 members are collectively running a Twitter account for the Distant Reading COST Action.	Researchers and students in the Humanities, Social Sciences, Computer Science and professionals in the Library world with an affinity for digitization and digital research methods.	We have more than 550 followers on Twitter as of November 2019. Our tweets typically receive 2000 "impressions" (views), many receive 5000, and some even receive more than 8000 impressions.	https://twitter.com/DistantReading
Publication of the "Distant Reading Recommends" series of blog posts.	Researchers in literary scholars and people more informally interested in literary	So far, we have been able to publish five blog posts in the "Distant Reading	https://www.distant-reading.net/category/distant-reading-recommends/

	<p>history across Europe. In "Distant Reading Recommends", an Action member introduces a novel, published between 1850 and 1920, from one of the participating countries in our Action. These novels may be important or notable within the individual nation's literary tradition, but less well-known in the broader European context. By bringing these novels to light, we aim to further advance our objectives of creating a broader, more inclusive, and better-grounded account of European literary history and cultural identity.</p>	<p>Recommends" series, written by scholars and concerning novels from Lithuania, Romania, Bulgaria, Serbia and Slovenia. We have reason to believe that the "Distant Reading Recommends" series has already garnered considerable attention. We plan to continue with blog posts in this series during the lifetime of the Action. One indicator if this are the number of "impressions" we see from the tweets promoting these posts on Twitter.</p>	
<p>Publication of the "Distant Reading Talks" series of video statements on Distant Reading.</p>	<p>Scholars in Literary Studies, Digital Humanities, Computational Linguistics and Computer Science.</p>	<p>The videos provide personal, scholarly perspectives on the issue of Distant Reading.</p>	<p>https://www.distant-reading.net/videos/</p>
<p>Creation and curation of a Zenodo community for "Distant Reading for European Literary History".</p>	<p>Scholars in Literary Studies, Digital Humanities, Computational Linguistics, Computational Literary Studies, Computer Science.</p>	<p>This Zenodo community makes various documents that we archive on Zenodo more visible as an ensemble. As such, it increases the visibility and findability of our outputs.</p>	<p>https://zenodo.org/communities/distant-reading/</p>
<p>Creation and curation of a Zenodo community for "European Literary Text Collection" (ETLeC)</p>	<p>Scholars in Literary Studies, Computational Literary Studies, Computational Linguistics, Digital Humanities, and Computer Science.</p>	<p>This collection unites all archive copies of the ELTeC collections in one place. In this way, it increases the visibility and findability of our ELTeC collections.</p>	<p>https://zenodo.org/communities/eltec/</p>
<p>The First Workshop on "Distant Reading in Portuguese" was organized on 27-28 October 2019 at the University of Oslo</p>	<p>Students, Early Career Investigators and other Scholars in Portuguese Linguistics and Literary Studies.</p>	<p>The workshop was successful in bringing the issue of Distant Reading into the local community of Portuguese Linguistics and Literary Studies.</p>	<p>https://translate.google.com/translate?sl=pt&tl=en&u=https%3A%2F%2Fwww.hf.uio.no%2Ffilos%2Fforskning%2Faktuelt%2Farrangementer%2Fgjesteforelesninger-seminarer%2F2019%2Fencontro-sobre-leitura-distante-em-portugues.html</p>
<p>Christof Schöch gave an interview to the SWR Radio Station.</p>	<p>The target audience of this activity is the general educated public.</p>	<p>This activity is likely to have brought considerable attention to the Action's key objectives.</p>	<p>https://www.uni-trier.de/fileadmin/fb2/LD/V/DH/digital-humanities.wav</p>
<p>Newspaper article about the Action: "Die europäische Literaturgeschichte wird neu geschrieben. Digital Humanities an Uni Trier bereiten Literatur neu auf"</p>	<p>The target audience of this dissemination activity is the general public in Germany.</p>	<p>This activity resulted in increased visibility of the Action's objectives in a local context. The article has been republished in several venues with high visibility in Germany, e.g.</p>	<p>https://www.wochenspiegelive.de/trier/stadt-trier/artikel/die-europaeische-literaturgeschichte-wird-neu-geschrieben-53978/</p>

		at IDW -- https://idw-online.de/de/news701449 -- and at KOWI -- https://www.kooperation-international.de/aktuelles/nachrichten/detail/info/digital-humanities-weltweites-netzwerk-erforscht-europaeische-literaturgeschichte/ .	
Action members are actively using a Facebook account for the Action.	The target audience of this activity is a broader audience of students and researchers in the Humanities.	So far, since the creation of the account in October 2019, almost 200 people already follow the Facebook account.	https://www.facebook.com/distantreading
The Action liaises actively with the Special Interest Group on "Digital Literary Stylistics" (SIG-DLS) within the Alliance of Digital Humanities Associations (ADHO).	Fellow researchers in Computational Literary Studies at the international level across Europe but notably beyond Europe.	The reach of our online dissemination efforts is expanded through the SIG-DLS network.	https://dls.hypotheses.org/168
We have added information about the Action to the project directory run by the European Association for Digital Humanities (EADH).	The target audience of this activity is fellow researchers in Digital Humanities broadly conceived across Europe.	The visibility of the Action has been enhanced by our presence on the EADH project directory.	https://eadh.org/projects/distant-reading-european-literary-history
Action member Justin Tonra has published an online magazine article on "What is distant reading?"	The publication venue, RTÉ Brainstorm Ireland, has researchers across the Natural Sciences, Social Sciences and Humanities as well as the general public interested in research as its target audience.	This article has produced a high level of visibility for the Action on the one hand, and for the more general issue of computational methods in the humanities, on the other hand.	https://www.rte.ie/brainstorm/2019/1114/1090846-what-is-distant-reading/
Action members have written an English-language Wikipedia article about "Distant Reading". This article will also be translated into several other European languages by Action members.	The target audience of this dissemination activity is the general, interested public.	An explanation of the key term in the name of our COST Action is now available on one of the most visited websites in the world.	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Distant_reading
At least one Action member has used ELTeC texts in their teaching: MA students in the 'Introduction to Digital Humanities' module have used novels from ELTeC for the purposes of completing an assignment on computational analysis of an unknown novel.	The target audience of this exploitation activity have been MA students in the "Digital Culture" programme at NUI Galway, Ireland.	The MA students have used authentic texts to gain experience with digital methods of analysis for literary texts.	http://www.nuigalway.ie/courses/taught-postgraduate-courses/digital-cultures.html
Several Action participants from Basel (CH) -- Simon Gabay, Berenike Herrmann, Simone Rebora -- have been organizing a	The target audience of this activity are primarily early career investigators in Literary Studies and Linguistics from Swiss	The participants will acquire competencies in the areas of digitization using Optical Character Recognition, corpus design, text	https://www.unil.ch/doc-digitalstudies/home/menuinst/activites-du-programme/distant-reading-tools-and-methods.html

training school on "Distant Reading – Tools and Methods" to take place in December 2019.	universities.	encoding and metadata management as well as analytical approaches to text collections.	
--	---------------	--	--

Exploitation activities

Please describe below any activities undertaken to ensure exploitation (use, in particular in a commercial context) of the Action's achievements.

Item/activity	Target audience	Outcome
We are in the process of building a conversion process that will allow us to transform the hundreds of novels contained in the ELTeC collections to EPUB for reading on ebook readers and we will publish these novels for reading on major, free, international ebook platforms.	The general public interested in reading famous novels as well as in discovering forgotten novels from across Europe in their original language.	Expected result: High level of visibility of our Action outside strictly academic circles, and new readership for the novels we have published.

DRAFT

Action Success(es)

Taking into account the achievements, impacts and policy implementation of the Action described in the preceding sections, please describe below the two most significant successes of the Action.

Description of the success	The creation of the European Literary Text Collection (ELTeC) is a key success, because it is the first comparable, massively multilingual, state-of-the-art, digital literary corpus of European literature. See key information here: https://www.distant-reading.net/eltec/
Dimensions of the success	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific breakthrough • Building capacity in bridging separate fields of science and technology

Description of the success	The successful application for a Horizon 2020 Starting Community called "Computational Literary Studies Infrastructure" that allows us to continue and expand research and community building begun in the COST Action.
Dimensions of the success	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific breakthrough • Building capacity in bridging separate fields of science and technology

DRAFT

Other matters

This section is confidential to the Management Committee, the Action Rapporteur and the COST Association, and is not included in the version of the report that is published on the COST website.

Added value of extension

The Action end date was extended beyond the original end date (four years after the first MC meeting of the Action) please describe below why this extension was necessary and the added value of the extension.

The pandemic has made progress difficult in several areas and the extension allowed us to complete a variety of ongoing activities, most notably completing ELTeC, investigations using ELTeC in WG2 and WG3, STSMs and the Final MC Meeting and Final Action Event. With the exception of the Final Action Event, which had to be held online-only regardless, these advantages have turned out to be the case.

Difficulties in implementing the Action

If any difficulties were experienced in the implementation of the Action (e.g. imbalances of participation across the Working Groups, inactive country representatives) please described these below. Please also describe the efforts made by the MC to address these.

Ever-shifting COST rules were a concern across the lifetime of the Action. Some changes represented a welcome simplification (such as the expanded coverage of the flat daily rate for travel), others were felt to be more of a challenge (establishing the number of unique participants in events, defining a per diem local organizer support that at the same time needs to be used for eligible expenses only and documented with bills in case of an audit). The e-COST system needs learning but is generally useful, especially the reliance on electronic administration only. Unfortunately, the grant holder's university does not participate in the electronic-only paradigm, creating large amounts of additional administrative overheads.

Suggestions for improvements to COST framework/ procedures

The mandate of the Scientific Committee includes providing advice to the COST Committee of Senior Officials on possible improvements to the COST framework. Please describe below any improvements that you believe should be made to the COST framework.

Simplify the scheme to calculate participants in events and make it better reflect actual expenses incurred (every participant needs room and drinks coffee every day, whether or not they are present for one day or for several days!). Remove the requirement for proof of eligible expenses when the daily per person rate for local organizer support is attributed.

Sustaining the network beyond the Action

Are there any plans to sustain the network beyond the end of the Action?

YES

Please describe how the network will be sustained beyond the end of the Action.

The network will be sustained beyond the end of the Action through the large follow-up project funded by Horizon 2020 in the Starting Community program and called "Computational Literary Studies Infrastructure" (CLS INFRA). For more information, see <https://clsinfra.io>.

Emerging topics/ developments in the field of the Action

Please describe any emerging topics or potentially important future developments identified during the Action and that could potentially be addressed by future COST activities such as Actions S&T Conferences or Exploratory Workshops.

DRAFT

Annex 1: Types of objectives

1 - Coordination of scientific and technological activities at a European level

- 1.a - Development of a common understanding/definition of the subject matter
- 1.b - Coordination of information seeking, identification, collection and/or data curation
- 1.c - Coordination of experimentation or testing
- 1.d - Comparison and/or performance assessment of a theory, model, methodology, technology or technique
- 1.e - Development of knowledge needing international coordination, pertaining to a new or improved theory, model, methodology, technology or technique
- 1.f - Achievement of a specific tangible output that cannot be achieved without international coordination (e.g. due to practical issues such as database availability, language barriers, availability of infrastructure or know-how, etc.)
- 1.g - Input to stakeholders (e.g. standardization body, policy-makers, regulators, users), excluding commercial applications
- 1.h - Input for future market applications (including cooperation with private enterprises)
- 1.i - Dissemination of research results to the general public
- 1.j - Dissemination of research results to stakeholders (excluding specific input in view of knowledge application)

2 - Community building

- 2.a - Building a community around a topic of scientific and/or socio-economic relevance, allowing for knowledge exchange and the development of a joint research agenda
- 2.b - Building a community around a new or emerging field of research
- 2.c - Bridging separate fields of science/disciplines to achieve breakthroughs that require an interdisciplinary approach
- 2.d - Acting as a stakeholder platform or trans-national practice community, pertaining to a certain area of socio-economical or societal application, or to a certain market sector
- 2.e - Building capacity in the demographic inclusiveness of networks in science and technology, including representation of newly established research groups, Early-Career Investigators, the under-represented gender and teams from countries/regions with less capacity in the field of the Action

Annex 2: Dimensions of successes

1 - Breakthroughs

- 1.a - Scientific breakthrough
- 1.b - Technological breakthrough
- 1.c - Breakthrough in socio-economic or societal applications

2 - Policy contribution

- 2.a - Contribution to regulatory policy
- 2.b - Contribution to environmental, infrastructural or agricultural policy
- 2.c - Contribution to economic or socio-economic policy
- 2.d - Contribution to social, cultural or legal policy

3 - Capacity building

- 3.a - Building capacity in an existing field of science and technology
- 3.b - Building capacity in bridging separate fields of science and technology
- 3.c - Building capacity in a new or emerging field of science and technology
- 3.d - Building capacity in valorising and implementing advances and applications in science and technology
- 3.e - Building capacity in the demographic inclusiveness of networks in science and technology, including representation of newly established research groups, Early-Career Investigators, the under-represented gender and teams from countries/regions with less capacity in the field of the Action

DRAFT